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Strategy for Implementing Novel Societal Applications of Accelerators

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ABSTRACT

IFAST Task 12.1 is studying novel and important applications of particle accelerators in the health, environmental, imaging and radioisotope production areas and has identified those with the most potential. For these, it has determined what steps are still required to deliver these in practice, what work is or needs to be done to do this and the strategy for doing this. To complement this, it has also been looking at the general barriers that discourage industry from implementing accelerators and how these might be overcome.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	5
2	TASK 12.1.2 – NOVEL FORMS OF RADIOTHERAPY	5
2.1	INTRODUCTION	5
2.2	VHEE	7
2.2.1	<i>Description of VHEE and importance</i>	<i>7</i>
2.2.2	<i>Accelerators and Accelerator technologies for VHEE RT.....</i>	<i>8</i>
2.2.3	<i>Normal Conducting RF linacs</i>	<i>9</i>
2.2.4	<i>Superconducting RF linacs</i>	<i>11</i>
2.2.5	<i>Laser Plasma Facilities</i>	<i>12</i>
2.2.6	<i>Accelerator Technologies for VHEE applications.....</i>	<i>12</i>
2.3	RADIOBIOLOGY AND CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS	14
2.4	FUTURE OUTLOOK AND STRATEGY FOR DELIVERY	15
2.5	REFERENCES FOR SECTION 2	16
3	TASK 12.1.3 - ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS OF ACCELERATORS.....	19
3.1	INTRODUCTION	19
3.2	IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEM	20
3.2.1	<i>Air Pollution</i>	<i>20</i>
3.2.2	<i>Water Pollution.....</i>	<i>20</i>
3.2.3	<i>Sewage Sludge</i>	<i>21</i>
3.3	DESCRIPTION OF POLLUTION CONTROL ACCELERATOR BASED TECHNOLOGIES	22
3.4	ACCELERATORS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS	24
3.5	STRATEGY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS	26
3.6	REFERENCES FOR SECTION 3	29
4	12.1.4 – ACCELERATOR IMAGING.....	29
4.3	STRATEGY TO REACH THESE GOALS	31
5	12.1.5 – RADIOPHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTION	32
5.1	INTRODUCTION	32
5.1	STATE OF ART	32
5.2	IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEM	34
5.2.1	<i>Production of 225Ac using low energy proton accelerators.....</i>	<i>34</i>
5.2.2	<i>Production of 225Ac using electron accelerators.....</i>	<i>35</i>
5.2.3	<i>Production of 225Ac via High Energy Proton Spallation of Thorium.....</i>	<i>35</i>
5.3	NOVEL ACCELERATOR FOR ISOTOPES PRODUCTION.....	36
5.4	STRATEGY TO DELIVER THIS APPLICATION	36
5.4.1	<i>Partners</i>	<i>36</i>
5.4.2	<i>Roadmap</i>	<i>37</i>
5.4.3	<i>Sources of founding</i>	<i>38</i>
5.5	CONCLUSIONS.....	38
5.6	REFERENCES	38
6	12.1.6 – OVERCOMING OBSTACLES TO ACCELERATOR USE.....	40
6.1	OBSTACLES PREVENTING ACCELERATOR ADOPTION BY INDUSTRY AND ENVIRONMENT CONTROL.....	40
6.2	SOLUTIONS IDENTIFIED	41
6.3	RECENT EXAMPLES OF ACCELERATOR USE.....	42
6.4	KEY RECOMMENDATIONS	43
7	CONCLUSIONS	43

8 ANNEX: GLOSSARY44

1 Introduction

Particle accelerators are already extensively used in health and industry for a wide range of applications, including cancer treatment, polymer modification, sterilisation of medical products, radioisotope production, imaging, phyto-sanitation, food treatment, etc. These exploit the unique features of the accelerated beams and the control the use of accelerators provides. Nevertheless, accelerators have a much greater potential which is currently not being fully exploited. This is due to many reasons, including a lack of knowledge in industry of what benefits they could bring, the perceived and real cost of the technology, the absence of the skills required to assess the potential for a specific industry and to implement the technology and concerns over safety and regulation.

Task 12.1 is trying to address these issues in two ways. The first is to study a number of novel applications of accelerators with the most potential. These are in the areas of health, the treatment of environmental contamination, imaging and radioisotope production. The second is to examine and address the main barriers in industry to the introduction of accelerators.

This document introduces a number of important novel applications with the most potential. It describes why they are important and how accelerators can help with each application. It also shows what steps are required to deliver these applications in practice and hence the strategy for delivering them. The applications are separated into the health, environmental, imaging and radioisotope production areas. In each case, the strategy follows the same basic steps:

- (1) Identifying the applications
- (2) Assessing the role of accelerators and what they can achieve
- (3) The specifications for the accelerators
- (4) Proof-of-principle
- (5) Business case
- (6) Delivery

All the applications discussed in this document are between steps 2 and 4.

The document also presents the general barriers to the adoption of accelerators by industry and summarises the progress in analysing and overcoming these barriers.

2 Task 12.1.2 – Novel Forms of Radiotherapy

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Radiotherapy (RT) is a fundamental component of effective cancer treatment and control. Ever since the discovery of X-rays in 1895, they played key role in cancer treatment. The first electron accelerator was designed by van de Graaff in 1924 [1] and it used high electric potentials (>10 kV) in order to accelerate charged particles. The most frequently used modality of RT uses high-energy (6 to 10 MeV) photons produced by electron linear accelerators (linacs). More than 15,000 electron linacs are currently used worldwide to treat patients.

However, conventional photon RT is characterised by almost exponential attenuation and absorption, and consequently delivers the maximum energy near the beam entrance, but continues to deposit significant energy at distances beyond the cancer target. RT with heavier charged particles, also called hadron therapy (HT) with protons and other ions species has also been proposed and offers several ballistic advantages over the classical RT with X-rays. Now, more than 70 years after the initial idea of using proton and heavier ion therapy, HT has eventually reached the critical time of transitioning from a limited number of specialized institutions to many particle-therapy centres worldwide. Currently, proton therapy is flourishing with over 100 HT facilities in the clinical practice and many are under construction or planning. Despite the recent progress of HT, numerous challenges and new opportunities are yet to be addressed to maximize clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness of this advanced therapy modality in order to make it: (a) applicable for treating larger number of tumours, (b) accessible for a greater number of patients globally. It worth noting, for example, that hadrons are exquisitely range sensitive – and hence the dose reposition is sensitive to any change in inhomogeneities present before the target tumour and if not properly accounted for in treatment planning can readily lead to healthy tissue receiving large doses [2, 3].

An interesting and unexplored possibility is the use of RT with higher energy electrons. Although, intermediate-energy electron (IEE) has historically been used to treat cancer for more than five decades. The relatively small extent of the depth-dose curve for such low energy electrons means that more healthy tissue is spared, compared to a photon treatment plan. However, this limitation can be overcome if the electron energy is increased as can be seen in Figure 2.1A.

Figure 2.1: A- TOPAS Monte Carlo simulations of the Percentage Dose Depth (PDD) profiles for various particle beams in a water phantom (beam widths $r=0.5$ cm) [2]. B- Focusing of e-beams (courtesy of A. Lagzda [2, 3]).

Figure 2.1 shows the dose profile for various particle beams in water and for electrons at 250 MeV the penetration becomes deeper and the transverse penumbra sharper, although the longitudinal penumbra is also increased but this can be reduced by focusing the electrons (Figure 2.1B). While the use of high energy electron beams (up to 50 MeV) has been already studied in the 80's by the Karolinska group (Brahme et al) their clinical implementation was not continued. More recently, the idea of investigating the use of very high-energy (50-250 MeV) electron (VHEE) beams for RT has gained interest. By increasing electron energies up to 50 - 250 MeV, deeper tissue penetration is possible.

2.2 VHEE

2.2.1 Description of VHEE and importance

The main advantages of VHEE beams over photons are related to the fact that 1) small diameter VHEE beams can be scanned and focused relatively easily, thereby producing finer resolution for intensity modulated treatments than photon beams. Also, VHEE beams are relatively insensitive to tissue heterogeneities [2], unlike protons for example, which are inherently range sensitive [2]. This allows increasing the therapeutic index of radiation therapy that is dependent on spatial dose distribution. 2) accelerators can be constructed at significantly lower cost compared to the current installations required for proton beam delivery and presents an interesting and possibly cost-effective option to treat cancer. 3) VHEE beam machine can conceivably operate at very high dose rates possibly compatible with the generation of the “FLASH effect” (i.e., to elicit normal tissue sparing and tumour killing).

The recent studies involving the ultra-high dose rate (UHDR) delivery (mean dose rate above 100 Gy/s) of ionizing radiation and termed FLASH radiotherapy (FLASH-RT), have uncovered some surprising and unexpected therapeutic benefits and has caused tremendous excitement in the radio-oncology field as it may revolutionize modern day RT [4]. Noteworthy too is the fact that the “FLASH effect” was and continues to be defined *in vivo*, a feature that portends its rapid clinical implementation and utility. This represents fundamentally a new prospect for increasing the therapeutic index of RT that can be combined with it for enhanced efficacy. Most of the preclinical data demonstrating the increased therapeutic index of FLASH has been using a single fraction of RT and using Intermediate Energy Electron (IEE) beams (6 MeV), that do not allow to treat deep seated tumours and trigger large lateral penumbra. This problem can be solved by using VHEE beams (> 50 MeV).

Radioresistant tumours have confounded curative intent in radiotherapy for decades and have motivated many of the enhancements in image-guided radiotherapy as well as the development of innovative RT modalities including Spatially Fractionated (SF) RT and FLASH. FLASH-RT is today defined as the ultrafast delivery of radiation at dose rates that are several orders of magnitude greater than those used in conventional radiotherapy (>40 Gy/s vs. 0.5-20 Gy/min, respectively).

The sparing of normal tissue when subjected to UHDR (FLASH) was first reported in 1959. However, limited studies on tumours were performed at that time and the common belief was that UHDR would spare tumours as well. In addition, due to technical limitations, it was relatively challenging to translate the results into clinical practice and further research on this new RT was severely limited. Today, in-depth progression of radiation source research and advances in radiobiology research, the great potential of FLASH-RT has been recognized again as a tool for clinical radiotherapy.

In most of the preclinical studies performed with IEE, proton and photons beams, radiation toxicity to healthy tissues was significantly reduced and tumour growth was inhibited, with a degree of tumour control similar to that of traditional dose rate irradiation [5]. However, despite many positive findings, it is important to note that a few studies have reported the absence of the FLASH effect using synchrotron photon [6], proton [7] and electron [8] beams. These negative results demonstrate that the optimal physical and biological parameters and experimental conditions remains to be fully

defined. This is mandatory to achieve reproducible and comparable experimental results that will ultimately promote the safe and reliable transfer of these strategies into the clinic. Given these challenges, VHEE beams provide the opportunity to explore the biological impact of UHDR ($>10^8$ Gy/s) and ultra short time scale of exposure (in the nano second range), whereas the dose rate produced by proton and photon FLASH beams is limited and in the range of couple of 100 Gy/s.

2.2.2 Accelerators and Accelerator technologies for VHEE RT

Today and after three decades of research in linear colliders on the Japanese Linear Collider (JLC) [9], the Next Linear Collider (NLC) [10], the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) [11] and more recently the Cool Copper Collider (C³) [12], it is possible to have compact high-gradient linacs (> 100 MV/m) based on Radio Frequency (RF) accelerating structures (AS), which make a compact VHEE radiation therapy accelerator a reality (Figure 2.2). Considerable research and development programs have been carried out under the framework of these High Energy Physics (HEP) Colliders projects to obtain the demanding performances of such accelerators. As a matter of example in the CLIC linac: an accelerating gradient of 100 MV/m, low breakdown rate, micron-tolerance alignment and a high RF-to-beam efficiency (around 30%) are envisaged [13-16]. Furthermore, the use of novel accelerator techniques such as Laser Plasma Accelerator (LPA) is also starting to be applied in the VHEE field.

Figure 2.2: CLIC RF X-band cavity prototype (12 GHz, 100 MV/m).

Dedicated VHEE experimental studies have been realized using Normal Conducting (NC) linac based accelerator facilities in NLTCa at SLAC and CLEAR at CERN giving very promising results for the use of VHEE electron beams. Furthermore some experimental tests have been carried out also with LPA sources, mainly laser driven, at ELBE-DRACO in HZDR [17], in the LOA in the Institut Polytechnique de Paris [18], the SCAPA facility [19] in the University of Strathclyde and the Istituto Nazionale di Ottica (INO) at Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) in Pisa [20], in Europe among others. In particular for FLASH with electron beams, biological studies have been carried out at intermediate-energies with the Kinetron linac [21] and more recently with the eRT6-Oriatron linac at CHUV [4], the ElectronFlash in the Institute Curie (IC) at Orsay or the similar ELF ElectronFlash

in Antwerpen [22, 23]. Experimental studies are also ongoing at very high-energies at CLEAR at CERN [24]. In the following a brief description of some accelerator facilities based on RF linacs and on LPA that are available currently or in the near future to perform VHEE studies. Although the list is not exhaustive it gives an example of the performance of the current machines.

2.2.3 Normal Conducting RF linacs

NC RF linac is the technology being used for most of the VHEE research. The main advantages of this technology are the flexibility and compactness.

The current and near future available machines for VHEE experiments using this technology are:

The CLEAR facility at CERN [24] is an electron NC X-band linac based on CLIC technology located in the experimental area of the CLIC Test Facility 3 (CTF3). The linac is capable of producing an electron beam with an energy 50-250 MeV, bunch charge 0.01-0.4 nC, transverse normalized emittance 3/30 μm for 0.05/0.5 nC, relative energy spread $< 0.2\%$, bunch length 200-1200 μm , repetition rate 1-5 Hz (25 with an upgrade), number of bunches 1 -150 with 1.5 GHz of micro bunch spacing [24]. The beam line includes transport and focusing elements, an experimental area currently used to test CLIC two-beam modules, and a complete set of beam diagnostics, including spectrometers before and after the experimental area [3] (Figure 2.3). A dedicated beam line for VHEE experiments is under study (ex: larger quadrupole aperture) that could also be a test prototype for a larger clinical machine. To carry out the technology development for CLIC, a worldwide collaboration, including groups working on many different applications is ongoing. In particular for medical applications, a FLASH facility based on a CLIC X-band 100 MeV linac is being designed in collaboration with CHUV to treat large, deep-seated tumours in FLASH conditions. The facility known as DEFT (Deep Electron FLASH Therapy) is compact so as to fit in a typical hospital campus.

Figure 2.3: CLEAR User Facility for VHEE Studies, (courtesy of R Corsini, W Farbolini and P Korysko).

The CLARA facility at Daresbury Laboratory [25, 26], CLARA Phase 1 is a NC S-band linac providing 40 MeV, 10 Hz, 100 pC e-beam. CLARA Phase 2 (estimated to be complete in 2025) will provide a source of electrons at clinically relevant energies up to 250 MeV for R&D in VHEE - for plasmid and cell irradiation, dosimetry, treatment planning. A dedicated beam exploitation area: FEBE (Full Energy Beam Exploitation) has been designed taking into consideration the experience of both completed and planned VHEE experiments on CLARA Phase 1, with flexibility and diagnostic capabilities (bunch charge, beam position, transverse and longitudinal profile diagnostics in the arc and the hutch beamline). It will provide an ideal test-bed for future VHEE studies. Furthermore potential in-air VHEE experiments have been considered during the design. FEBE design and procurement is planned in readiness for “Proof-of-principle”, “High Impact” experiments expected in 2025.

AWA at ANL [27] is a NC X-band linac with an energy range between 6-63 MeV, bunch charge 0.1-100 nC, transverse normalized emittance 0.5/240 μm , bunch length 0.1-3 mm, repetition rate 0.5-10 Hz, with the possibility of longitudinal shaping (train, tringle, rectangle and trapezoid). A beamline with large chambers to host structures, Be window for moderate vacuum, several DUT test areas, measurement of charge, power, energy, beam shape, emittance and bunch length and shielding room to improve signal-to-noise ratio are available.

ThePITZ facility at **DESY** (Zeuthen) [28] is a NC photoinjector capable of producing an electron beam with an energy up to 22 MeV. It can offer a bunch pattern with customized time structure: bunch trains of up to 1ms length and bunch repetition rate within a train (0.1 - 1 MHz, optimum 4.5 MHz). Trains can be repeated with up to 10 Hz: from 1 to 1000 bunches in 1 ms (optimum up to 4500) and from 1 to 10 000 bunches in 1 s (optimum up to 45 000). Depending on bunch charge, individual bunches can have: length of 0.1- 60 ps (bunch compressor) and spot size down to ~100 μ m. An energy upgrade up to 250 MeV, known as FLASHLab, is foreseen by means of a SC XFEL type cryomodule and with a dedicated experimental radiobiology line.

The ARES facility at DESY (in Hamburg) [29] is based on NC S-band linacs which provide beam energies from 20 up to 160 MeV. The beamline includes transport and focusing magnets, and a complete set of beam diagnostics, including spectrometers. A combination of velocity bunching and variable magnetic chicane facilitates provision of ultra-short bunches. An advanced, polarizable X-band Transverse Deflecting Structure (TDS) is installed for beam characterisation. A dedicated experimental area, in-air (separated from the machine vacuum by a 50 μ m thick titanium foil), equipped with beam diagnostics and linear stages is mainly used for medical experiments in the frame of VHEE and imaging methods with electrons. Of special interest is the potential to perform in-vivo experiments (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: ARES User Facility for VHEE Studies (courtesy of F Burkardt).

2.2.4 Superconducting RF linacs

SC technology is also being used but is less extended for these type of applications. Some facilities mainly in Europe are starting to be available for VHEE experiments.

ELBE [17] Center of High Power Radiation Sources at **HZDR** in Dresden, offers a SCRF (1.3 GHz XFEL type) linac with maximum 40 MeV energy (50 MeV with RF pulsing), bunch charge 0.01-80 pC, repetition rate from single pulse up to 13 MHz, macro pulse length 0.1 ms-CW and transverse normalized emittance of less than 15 μ m.

2.2.5 Laser Plasma Facilities

LPA technology is a very dynamic field and an enormous number of laser facilities are booming worldwide. The performance of the electrons beams are improving and are starting to be considered for applications. For example, in Europe facilities having VHEE dedicated applications include:

DRACO at **ELBE** [30, 31] Center of High Power Radiation Sources at **HZDR** is 1 PW Laser system providing 50-400 MeV electrons by LPA (laser driven) with up to 500 pC bunch charge, 10 fs pulse length, 5 mrad divergence and 1 Hz repetition rate. A radiobiology VHEE program is ongoing with a dedicated beam line and first feasibility biology experiments have been published last year [32].

LOA at **IPP** [18] is laser driven wakefield plasma electron acceleration delivering an electron beam with a maximum energy in the range of 100 -150 MeV, depending on laser depletion and with a maximum charge in the range of 10 pC to few nC depending on injection mechanism and on saturation of the accelerating structure. A new beamline dedicated to medical applications known as IDRA is being constructed. The new beamline will provide stable experimental conditions for radiobiology and dosimetry R&D.

ILIL at **INO** [20] is a PW laser able to accelerate electrons in the VHEE energy range, with a charge per bunch between 100 to 200 pC in the selected spectral range with a current repetition rate in the Hz-scale and being upgraded to 100 Hz in the next future. A dedicated beamline for radiobiology and dosimetry experiments exists and is being mainly used for VHEE studies.

2.2.6 Accelerator Technologies for VHEE applications

Recent advances in RF accelerator technology, especially in the high-gradient RF structures where more than 100 MeV/m are now achievable in the lab environment are transforming the landscape for VHEE RT. VHEE RT requires beam energies between 50-200 MeV, an improved dose conformity and scale to higher doses rates, in the case of the FLASH-RT until 50 Gy/s are needed. Novel high gradient technologies could enable ultra-compact structures, with higher repetition rates and higher currents.

An international R&D global effort is being made by labs such as: CERN, INFN, KEK, MIT, UCLA, LANL, SLAC, AWA-AN, university group such as the Tsinghua University HG lab and industry partners and focused towards:

- Material origin and purity, surface treatments, manufacturing technology
- Consistency and reproducibility of test results.

Some promising R&D are:

The distributed coupling accelerator developed at SLAC [33] (Figure 2.5) to more efficiently and uniformly distribute the RF power into the AS and minimise electrical breakdown.

Figure 2.5: X-band cavity prototype with 3D distributed coupling (courtesy of S. Tantawi and E. Snively-SLAC)

The use of cryogenic copper is transforming the linac design offering a new frontier from the perspective of beam brightness, overall efficiency, peak RF power requirements, and overall costs. Operation at 77 K (liquid nitrogen) results in a minor decrease in efficiency for establishing gradients with a dramatic reduction in cost and increase in performance. Experiments have shown: increased conductivity and hardness enabling higher gradients, increase in quality factor of 2.5 factor. High-power cryogenics X-band structures have been realized to confirm the RF performance and to measure the breakdown rates, 150 MeV are already demonstrated in lab conditions [34]. A new Higgs collider using this technology, known as C³ [12] is being designed and a facility to test this technology with a beam is envisaged.

Another approach for the next generation of compact, efficient and high performance VHEE accelerator is the use of higher frequency millimetric waves (~100 GHz) and higher repetition rates using THz sources. Different structures at 110 GHz have been built and tested to 230 MV/m gradients with split cell and diffusion bonding at SLAC. Similar tests with laser-triggered semiconductor switch for pulse shaping (few-100s nanoseconds) are also ongoing at MIT. Improvements are ongoing to mitigate the breakdown problem at high-powers (600-800 kW) [35]. Finally relativistic electron sources with charges of 160 nC delivered in 1 second, with high repetition rate (ultimately 400Hz) utilizing field emission (100 fC per bunch, 40 ns pulse) are being developed by SLAC NSF program. An electron source as well as the associated diagnostics suitable to determine emittance, energy spread and modelling of transport, is in fabrication and will be commissioned in the near future.

Concerning the LPA technologies and in particular for the medical applications, the main challenges are:

- Beam performance and availability
- Consistency and reproducibility of test results.

These issues are currently the subject of a wide global study and in particular highlighted in the EU networks: EUPRAXIA [36] and I.FAST [37].

In the two cases robust and more compact global facilities have to be developed to adapt the facilities to a clinical environment.

2.3 RADIOBIOLOGY AND CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

VHEE beams exhibit several promising features for radiotherapy. They have sufficient penetrative ability to treat deep-seated tumours (at depths of 30 cm or more) with reduced entrance doses compared to photons and reduced penumbra spreading. The high charge-to-mass ratio of electrons allows for rapid scanning and focused delivery within the patient, further minimizing dose to healthy tissues. VHEE beams also demonstrate relative insensitivity to changes in patient geometry and inhomogeneities, enhancing their suitability for treatment. VHEE therapy requires compact and high-gradient linear accelerator (linac) solutions to accommodate existing treatment suites and minimize space constraints. These linacs need to be reliable, affordable, and capable of accelerating electrons to energies higher than those currently used in clinical environments. However, until recently, the radiobiology and preclinical experiments were limited by the availability of VHEE beams. Nonetheless, to realize the clinical potential of VHEE, the effects on biological structures and the Relative Biological Effectiveness (RBE) must be understood and there have been several studies in the University of Manchester group investigating the RBE and cell survival. These investigations have focussed on plasmids and on lung and prostate cells [38].

There are indeed similar limitations for FLASH research and development, as at present there are only a limited number of existing facilities able to operate and deliver doses at ultra-high dose rates. Experimental electron beams such as the kinetron at the Institut Curie and the Oriatron/eRT6 at the CHUV RV in [4]) were used to produce most of the preclinical FLASH studies available to date. More recently, biological results were reproduced with proton RV in [39] and photon beams (RV in [40]). But the UHDR that can be achieved with VHEE beams override any other technology and might be the best strategy to implement FLASH in the clinic.

One important benefit of FLASH as compared to radiotherapy at conventional dose rate, is that FLASH is delivered in tenths of a second and therefore has the capability of reducing the impact on organ or tumour motion. This is crucial since controlling motion remains an intense subject of research in the radiooncology field during the past decade. The second benefit comes from normal tissue sparing, whereas no data to date has found FLASH to protect tumours from the sterilizing effects of radiation. Various studies performed using single dose and single fraction provide convincing evidence that in tumours in xenograft (breast, prostate, lung, GBM), orthotopic (lung, GBM) as well as in genetically engineered mice models demonstrated that FLASH is as efficient as conventional dose rate radiotherapy to control tumours growth and induce complete response (RV in

[4, 5]. Very recent results also suggest that a third and major benefit might be realized as FLASH seems to overcome extrinsic radiation resistance factors such as hypoxia and immuno-depletion.

Since fractionated RT regimens are the standard of care for the treatment of solid tumours, it was essential to evaluate the impact of fractionation and assess whether FLASH-RT when delivered in fractionated regimen still spares normal tissue and eradicate tumours. Recent evidence suggest that this is the case as hypo-fractionated FLASH regimen maintained tumour response and neurocognitive sparing [41] and standard fractionation preserved synoptic functionality in the brain.

In summary, this differential response between normal tissue and tumours triggered by FLASH combined with VHEE characteristics might offer an unique opportunity for the field of radiation oncology to enhance tumour control in a safe and more efficacious manner. In addition, as hypofractionated regimens are becoming the standard of care for the treatment of a variety of tumour types, the capability to dose escalate with FLASH radiotherapy facilitates these approaches, and minimizes the number of patient visits that should minimise the cost of healthcare and maximise patient throughput.

2.4 FUTURE OUTLOOK AND STRATEGY FOR DELIVERY

Although VHEE beams show promise, several challenges remain. Further studies and experiments are necessary to optimize dose delivery methods and reduce the entrance dose, potentially through quadrupole magnet focusing. Additionally, the development of image-guided radiation therapy (IGRT) specific to VHEE treatments is crucial, considering the unique requirements and constraints of delivering treatment at ultra-high dose rates.

From the accelerator technology point of view an important point is to assess the possibility of focusing [42] and scanning transversely the beam, thereby overcoming the disadvantages associated in the past with low and intermediate energy electron and photon beam irradiation. Stability, reliability and repeatability are other mandatory ingredients for accelerators to be operated in a medical environment.

The major challenge for VHEE-FLASH is the delivery of a very high dose-rate, possibly over a large area, providing a uniform dose distribution throughout the target. Also the parameter window in which the FLASH effect takes place has still to be thoroughly defined, as well as its effectiveness as a function of the physical parameters of the electron beam. This, together with a clear understanding of the underlying biological processes will likely prove to be essential in order to fully optimize the FLASH RT technique. Finally, of particular importance, is the development of reliable on-line dosimetry for very high dose rates, a regime not adapted to the current standard dosimetry techniques for RT. Ionization chambers, routinely used in medical linacs, suffer from nonlinear effects at very high dose rates, and in order to get reliable measurements R&D is needed to develop novel ion chamber types, or explore alternative possibilities such as solid state detectors or the use of calibrated beam diagnostics.

All this asks for a large beam test activity, in order to experimentally characterize VHEE beams and their ability to produce the FLASH effect, and provide a test bed for the associated technologies. It is also important to compare the properties of the electron beams depending on the way they are produced, (RF linac or LPA technologies). A number of experimental test facilities are already or in the near future available to perform these ambitious objectives.

Regarding the linac design in the energy range of interest for VHEE applications there are different possibilities offering the desired performances and compactness with different degrees of technology maturity. The S-band technology is the most mature one, HG compact linacs of this type are already available from various industrial partners. The C-band and X-band RF linacs are still less mature and are mainly constructed in the labs with the help of industry for the machining, but these offer the prospect of high gradient acceleration and hence allow high energies to be achieved over a relatively short linac. In recent times, a considerable effort is being made from the industrialization point of view. Furthermore, future facilities as exemplified by the CERN-CHUV facility are also on the horizon. In summary an important R&D effort to apply these technologies in the medical field is ongoing and if successful could be a step further in the quest for compact and efficient VHEE RT in the range of hundred MeV.

For achieving these aims, a synergistic and multidisciplinary research effort based on accelerator technology as well as physical and radiobiological comparisons to see how well VHEE can meet the current assumptions and become a clinical reality is needed.

In summary, VHEE RT has the potential to revolutionize cancer treatment by offering improved dose distribution and reduced radiation to healthy tissues. Advances in compact and high-gradient linac solutions, treatment planning, and dose optimization techniques are key to translating VHEE theory into clinical practice. Continued research and development efforts are needed to overcome challenges and optimize VHEE radiotherapy for the benefit of cancer patients.

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3 Task 12.1.3 - Environmental Applications of Accelerators

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Technologies based on electron accelerators applications aimed at ensuring the safety of gaseous and liquid effluents discharged to the environment have been developed. It has been demonstrated that electron beam (EB) - based technologies for flue gas treatment (SO_x and NO_x removal) at coal and oil fired power plants, wastewater purification, and sludge hygienization and biohazards control can be effectively deployed to mitigate environmental degradation. Byproducts of flue gas purification and sludge hygienization are high value fertilizer, which is a great contribution of radiation technology to circular economy scheme implementation. Emerging technologies are now focused to encourage ballast water and ship diesel off-gases treatment to follow recent standards introduced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). The remarkable R&D works concerning sludge hygienization, marine diesel off gases treatment and ballast water treatment have been developed in the frame of ARIES and IFAST projects. Recently, extensive work has been carried out on the use of

EB for environmental remediation, which also includes the removal of emerging contaminants such as VOCs, endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), and potential EDCs. Persistent and stable organic pollutants generated by human socioeconomic activities pose a substantial environmental threat owing to their wide applications in industrial and consumer good. Therefore, all these technologies are an important supplement of conventional technologies in preserving a clean environment for our global future.

3.2 IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEM

Rapid population growth combined with industrialization, urbanization, and energy intensive lifestyles has resulted in severe problems to the environment, especially in large cities. In many countries where industry is concentrated in urban areas, severe air and water pollution problems have arisen in most of the large cities. Therefore, the pollution control has become an important subject in the field of environmental engineering.

3.2.1 Air Pollution

Fossil fuel combustion leads to acidic pollutants such as SO_2 , NO_x , HCl and PAH emission. Pollutants are emitted to the atmosphere with off-gassing from industry, power stations, residential heating systems, and municipal waste incinerators. Fossil fuels, which include coal, natural gas, petroleum, shale oil, and bitumen are the main source of heat and electrical energy. Recently, the main fuel used for renewable energy production in heat boilers is biomass as well. Gross emission of pollutants is tremendous in most countries all over the world. These pollutants are present in the atmosphere in such conditions that they can affect humans and their environment.

Recently, there has been significant concern about the air pollution from marine sources that currently utilize low quality diesel fuels. Three new regulations aiming to reduce maritime greenhouse gas emissions and the environmental impact of ships were introduced on 1st January 2023 by the International Maritime Organisation (IMO). As a result, research and development projects have focused heavily on creating a cost-effective technology that can clean off gases with a high level of efficiency. Exhausts from marine engines contain nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide and water vapor as well as nitrogen oxides, sulfur oxides, carbon monoxide, various hydrocarbons and complex particulate matter. The maritime transporters usually use heavy fuel oil (HFO) with a high content of sulfur, which naturally leads to the three main pollutants derived from shipping: nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur oxides (SO_x) and particulate matter (PM). Around 15% of global NO_x and 5–8% of SO_x emissions are attributable to ocean-going ships. SO_2 emission as a smog component is a precursor to acid rain and it can have a negative influence on plant life as well as on wider ecosystems.

3.2.2 Water Pollution

Increasing urbanization in the last two centuries has been accompanied by an expansion of sewage collection systems without any or adequate treatment. Liquid waste loads have become so large that the self-purification capacity of receiving streams down-stream of large populations can no longer prevent adverse effects on water quality. These wastes now constitute significant sources of water pollution. The industrial effluents carry chemical contaminations such as heavy metals, organic pollutants, petrochemicals, pesticides and dyes, while the discharge of sewage and sludge gives rise to microbiological and chemical contamination of water bodies. The discharge of such materials into

water bodies is responsible for risk of infection, health effects caused by contaminated drinking water and offensive odours. Therefore, all these industrial and municipal wastewater need adequate treatment at mostly biological type Waste Water Treatment Plants (WWTP). Organic pollutants pose a much greater challenge because they are usually very difficult to biodegrade, among which, endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) merit special attention. In most cases, these contaminants are not present in the water alone but in mixtures. Such situations are dangerous because there is still very little knowledge about undesirable synergistic effects. Many of these chemicals are not required to be monitored as they have no regulatory status. Increasingly, these compounds are detected in natural and drinking waters and wastewaters at relatively low concentration levels (ng dm^{-3} and $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$, respectively), however, long-term exposure of living organisms to these contaminants is still under investigation. No effective technologies have yet been developed to remove all these contaminants simultaneously, even though some contaminants have been shown to decompose by a certain degree in selected processes.

The main means of transport for global trade is ocean shipping and nowadays around 90% of traded goods are carried over the waves. The discharge of sea water used for ballasting ships poses a threat to coastal ecosystems. The introduction of alien species from ballast water discharge may lead to excessive development of these organisms in the new environment and cause a threat to native plant and animal communities. Low salinity is the basic natural factor shaping the biodiversity of the Baltic Sea and results in a small species diversity in comparison with other seas. Therefore, brackish seas, such as the Baltic Sea, are particularly sensitive to newly introduced species because they are poor in native species. In 2004, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) developed the Convention on the Control and Management of Ship's Ballast Water (BWM Convention), which provides a uniform legal regulation of the ballast water problem around the world. In accordance with the legal requirements, ships, including docks, may only discharge ballast water if the number of microorganisms in the discharged water does not exceed: for *Vibrio cholerae* (contagious) less than 1 colony forming unit (cfu) per 100 mL or less than 1 cfu per 1 g (wet weight) of zooplankton samples; *Escherichia coli* less than 250 cfu per 100 mL; *Enterococci* (intestinal) less than 100 cfu per 100 mL. A ship, before entering a shipyard, has to replace the ballast water (with its antibiological treatment) in open waters. However, some waters still remain, together with solid state sediments containing biological contamination. When the ship is placed on the dry dock for maintenance (repair, painting, etc.), this ballast water has to be discharged. The treatment technologies are applied to reduce microbiological contamination.

3.2.3 Sewage Sludge

Sewage sludge, also known as biosolid, is the solid waste yield after completion of the secondary stage of biological wastewater treatment (WWTP). The annual production of sewage sludge has been increasing around the world as stricter clean water regulations have begun to take effect. It is a rich source of both many micronutrients and fixed nitrogen, making it a valuable fertilizer. It is, however, highly contaminated and strong control measures are required before it can be used in this way.

3.3 DESCRIPTION OF POLLUTION CONTROL ACCELERATOR BASED TECHNOLOGIES

Different control technologies are proposed for fossil fuels off gases treatment; however, the most popular method is a combination of wet FGD (flue gas desulfurization) and SCR (selective catalytic reduction). The first, using lime or limestone slurry, leads to SO₂ capture and gypsum as a product. In the second process, ammonia is used as a reagent, and nitrogen oxides are reduced over a catalyst surface to gaseous nitrogen, which removes NO_x. A new advanced method uses EB for simultaneous SO₂ and NO_x removal. After irradiation of pollutant gas, fast electrons interact with the gas creating various ions and radicals; the primary species formed include e⁻, N₂⁺, N⁺, O₂⁺, O⁺, H₂O⁺, OH, H⁺, CO₂⁺, CO⁺, N₂^{*}, O₂^{*}, N, O, H, OH, and CO. In the case of a high water vapor concentration, the oxidizing radicals [•]OH and HO₂[•], and excited ions such as O(³P), are the most important radiolysis products. The SO₂, NO, NO₂, and NH₃ present cannot compete with the reactions because of very low concentrations, but react with N, O, OH, and HO₂ radicals. Ammonia is added to the gas to neutralize acids that are formed in reaction; aerosolized ammonium sulfate and nitrate are the final product of the reaction. The obtained byproduct is a high-quality fertilizer that can be used directly or as a substrate for NPK blends manufacturing. The soluble part of the byproduct is almost pure ammonium sulfate (98–99 %) with some amount of ammonium nitrate.

The treatment of off gases from diesel ship diesel generators require, due to high NO_x concentration, application of other modified technology. A new, hybrid technology is based on the concept of combining two methods used to clean up the exhaust gases: Electron Beam (EB) and Wet Scrubbing. A new emerging hybrid technology that couples the Electron Beam with the reduced size wet scrubbing methods may provide an answer to reducing emissions from the marine shipping industry. There are two main stages involved: (1) SO₂ and NO_x (mainly nonsoluble and nonreactive NO) oxidation during irradiation by the Electron Beam from the accelerator and (2) the transformed by irradiation well soluble pollution products (SO₃ and NO₂) absorption into aqueous solution. The technology has been developed by INCT and tested in Warsaw, Poland in laboratory scale and in pilot plant scale at Riga Shipyard (RTU, CERN, FEP, INCT, Biopolinex) with application of mobile accelerator system developed by Fraunhofer FEP of Dresden (Germany). The tests have been carried out in the frame of ARIES Innovative Project and INCT being a developer of the process received a patent.

Recent tests have illustrated the possibility of process applications to treat the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) and volatile organic compounds (VOC), including chlorinated VOCs, present in off-gases in trace concentrations.

A large number of substances present in wastewater such as hard surfactants, lignins, and pesticides cannot be degraded by conventional biochemical methods. Thus, they escape from decomposition in biological treatment. Biodegradation quality of wastewater depends on the oxidation level and structure of pollutants. Preliminary oxidation and fragmentation of biologically resistant molecules contribute to the improvement of their biodegradability. EB processing of wastewater is non-chemical and uses fast formation of short lived reactive radicals that can interact with a wide range of pollutants. High-energy irradiation produces instantaneous radiolytic transformations by energy transfer from

high energy accelerated electrons to orbital electrons of water molecules. Absorbed energy disturbs the electron system of the molecule and results in breakage of interatomic bonds. Such reactive radicals are strong oxidizing or reducing agents that can transform the pollutants in the liquid wastes. EB treatment of wastewater leads to purification by the decomposition of pollutants as a result of their reactions with highly reactive species formed from water radiolysis: hydrated electrons, $\cdot\text{OH}$ free radicals, and H atoms.

High reactivity is characteristic of water radiolysis products. The typical time of their reactions with impurities in water is less than 1 ms. H_2O_2 and $\cdot\text{OH}$ and $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radicals are oxidizing species, while H atoms and e_{aq}^- are reducing. Simultaneous existence of strong oxidants and strong reductants within wastewater under treatment is remarkable and important characteristics of radiation processing. For practical and safety reasons, the installations used for water, wastewater, and sludge treatment are mostly based on the electron beam. The absence of secondary radioactivity and the ability to switch off power quickly, which results in the absence of radiation, is particularly safe for staff and the local community. A particularly important property of radiation technologies, compared to other AOPs, is that they are non-selective processes that can be used to degrade compounds with different structures and properties. A unique advantage in relation to other AOPs is the possibility of the simultaneous degradation of pollutants by oxidation and reduction. Practically, radiation technologies do not require the use of additional reactants; in some cases, such addition significantly increases the effectiveness of the process. The most important advantage of radiation technologies, especially those using electron beams, is the relatively short time period required compared to other AOPs, which allows for obtaining satisfactory results. The major barrier to radiation technologies are economic factors, especially those related to the large investment costs necessary at the plant construction stage. This subject has been studied at IFAST as well.

Other possible an accelerator application is ballast water treatment. On the laboratory scale EB hybrid method has been developed in the frame of IFAST project with technical and financial contribution of REMONTOWA SHIPBUILDING S.A. The tests have been performed for 10 ships arriving from the different regions. For the controlled pathogens, the D_{10} dose [kGy] resulting in a 10-fold reduction in the population is as follows: *Vibrio cholerae*, *V.parahaemolyticus*, *V.vulnificus*, $D_{10} = 0.1$ kGy ; *E. coli* $D_{10} = 0.5$ kGy ; *Enterococci* $D_{10} = 0.6$ kGy. The lethal effect of ionizing radiation on marine organism of different size was also confirmed. The biological species and solid particulate matter were separated from the water stream by mechanical screening and membrane processes can be used to recirculate water for technological use.

The municipal water treatment plant excess sludge to be used as organic fertilizer must be hygenized. High energy ionizing radiation (EB) has the ability to inactivate pathogens with a very high degree of reliability and in a clean and efficient manner. Ionizing radiation interacts with matter both directly and indirectly. Direct interaction takes place with critical molecules such as DNA and proteins present in microorganisms, thus causing cell death. During indirect interaction, radiolysis products of water result in the formation of highly reactive intermediates that then react with the target biomolecules, culminating in cell death. The use of EB treatments allows for the complete elimination of nematodes and parasitic eggs (*Ascaris sp.*, *Trichuris sp.*, *Toxocara sp.*, ATT) and the practical elimination of

pathogens, such as contagious bacterial contamination and *Coliform* titer (decreased by three orders of magnitude for dose 1 kGy), *Clostridium perfringens* titer (decreased by five orders of magnitude for a dose of 1 kGy). The irradiated sludge being pathogen free can then be beneficially used as manure in the agricultural fields as it is rich in nutrients required for the soil. Since the irradiated sludge is free from bacteria, this can also be used as a medium for growing useful bacteria like *rhizobium* and *azetobacter* to produce biofertilizers, which can be used to enhance the crop yields. A new concept “zero energy” biogas plant is based on the construction of a complex system consisting of a biogas plant and an electron accelerator in the biofertilizer manufacturing line. Digested material (in which organic solids were decomposed into stable substances) originating from the methane fermentation of sewage sludge is irradiated to remove all pathogens using an electron beam from an accelerator powered by electric energy obtained from burning biogas in a co-generator. The product is a high quality, biologically safe fertilizer. As a result of T 12.2. IFAST-MS59 basic engineering validated by design office has been prepared.

3.4 ACCELERATORS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

In the field of radiation processing technology, microwave source-powered linear accelerators, single resonant cavity accelerators and direct current accelerators are being applied. The differences between the types of accelerators depend on the methods of generating accelerating electrons. To create electrical fields, two fundamental techniques have been used: direct-acting high-voltage power supplies for accelerators, and radio or microwave frequency generators for resonators, which use the electrical component of electromagnetic waves to accelerate particles (figure 3.1). Microwave accelerators (GHz), RF (low radiofrequency, 100 to 200 MHz), and DC (continuous beam) have all evolved into the workhorses of radiation processing and are widely used. Transformer accelerators dominate industrial applications with considerations of achieving high beam power with high efficiency. Accelerators of this type are being built to accelerate electrons up to 5 MeV.

Figure 3.1: Electron accelerators applied in radiation processing: (A) direct high voltage accelerators; (B) single cavity radiofrequency accelerators; (C) linear microwave accelerators. 1 – electron gun, 2 –focusing coil, 3 – scanning electromagnet, 4 - foil window.

Most often transformer accelerators have an energy of 0.15 to 1 MeV. The process of electrons acceleration to the energy of 5 to 10 MeV, necessary for radiation processing of bigger volume objects or materials having higher density, requires the use of resonance methods. These approaches for electron acceleration use the electrical component of the electromagnetic wave with a microwave range of 1,300 to 3,000 MHz formed in many small concentric resonators. Low energy efficiency (up to 10 %) and the high prices of these devices limit their industrial usage in the environmental applications. Better possibilities are offered by systems resonant powered by frequencies in the range of 100 MHz. In these systems instead of expensive sources of microwave energy (klystrons, magnetrons) relatively cheap generators using vacuum tubes of large power are applied. The accelerator’s efficiency also increases significantly (up to 50 %). Electron accelerators nowadays can be considered multipurpose machines that deliver beams with different energies and power levels. The most suitable type of electron accelerator for a certain application is defined by the required electron energy, which is related to the density and structure of objects to be irradiated. It is also classified by the beam power, which defines the total processing capacity of the installation. A variety of industrial electron accelerators can now provide electron energies from 0.3 MeV to more than 10 MeV with average beam power capabilities up to 700 kW. The creation of new, highly powerful electron accelerators that can be utilized for online processing of enormous flow streams of liquid or gaseous contaminants was a unique input for the technological advance’s application. The accelerators were set up in an extremely efficient installation and used for the process of treatment of wastewater and off-gas. However, to make this method of production competitive, further advancements in accelerator technology are required for the implementation of these processes. That is because the machines need to have a great deal of power, high energy consumption performance, and a high degree of dependability to work in challenging industrial sectors.

Performance limits for electron accelerators used in radiation processing

Parameter	Direct DC	UHF 100 to 200 MHz	Linac 1.3 to 9.3 GHz
Beam average current	< 2 A	< 100 mA	< 30 mA
Electrons energy	0.05 to 5 MeV	0.3 to 10 MeV	2 to 10 MeV
Beam power	~500 kW	700 kW	150 kW
Electrical efficiency	60 to 80 %	20 to 50 %	10 to 20 %

Selected accelerators for radiation processing [5].

Manufacturer	Accelerator or type	Energy [MeV]	Current [mA]	Power [kW]	Price* [M\$]	Cost [\$/W]

IBA, Belgium	UHF	10	15	150	6.1	40.7
RDI, U.S.A.	DC	5	50	250	4.9	19.6
NHV, Japan	DC	5	30	150	5.0	13.3
Vivirad, France	DC	5	200	1000	4.4	4.4
INP, Russia	UHF	5	10	50	1.2	24.0
INP, Russia	DC	1	500	400	2.0	5.0

3.5 STRATEGY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

Argonne National Laboratory [1] held a workshop exploring the energy and ecological uses of accelerators. R&D thrusts and the implications these advancements would have upon increasing accelerator capacity and efficiency targets are discussed in the workshop’s conclusions, which are provided in the publication as a table. The following are the main obstacles to the widespread use of technology connected to accelerators; (i) the absence of accelerator devices that are capable of operating at full-scale industrial levels, which tend to be at least ten times beyond the current state of the art; (ii) the necessity of developing accelerator systems that can be significantly reliable and efficient while remaining competitive with existing technological advances; (iii) the lack of pilot levels applications for these new technologies to show their efficiency and efficacy. It is feasible to compare these needs with the market condition currently using specified data.

Mapping of accelerator capabilities to application needs [1]

		Energy and environment applications						
		Wastewater	Sludge	Flue Gas	Medical waste	Environmental Remediation	Asphalt treatment	Emerging applications
Capabilities	Demo/pilot scale 0.5 MW; 0.5-1.5 MeV	1	2	2	1	1	3	1
	MW-class DC system 1 MW; 1-2 MeV	1	2	1	2	2	2	1
	MW-class high-energy 1 MW; 10 MeV	2	1	3	1	1	1	1
	Ten MW-class high-energy 10 MW; 10 MeV	2	1	3	3	1	1	1

1	Very important
2	Somewhat important
3	Not important or not applicable

R&D thrusts and the impact that progress in those thrusts would make on reaching accelerator capability and performance targets [1].

		Target Accelerator Capabilities			
		Demo/pilot scale (0.5 MW, 0.5-1.5 MeV)	MW-class DC system (1 MW, 1-2 MeV)	MW-class high-energy (1 MW, 10 MeV)	Ten MW-class high-energy (10 MW, 10 MeV)
R&D Thrusts	DC Systems: HV, high current	1	1	3	3
	NCRF Linac Systems: structures, performance	3	3	1	2
	SRF Linac Systems: structures, performance	2	3	1	1
	Beam Dynamics	2	1	1	1
	Electron Sources	2	1	1	1
	RF Power Systems: higher efficiency, lower cost	3	3	1	1
	SRF materials and cavity fabrication	3	3	1	1
	RF delivery components	3	3	1	1
	Beam windows	3	2	2	1
	Portability, field-ability	2	2	2	2
	System-level demonstration	2	1	1	1
	Commercialization viability	2	1	1	1

1	Very important
2	Somewhat important
3	Not important or not applicable

Connelly et al. [3] examine the potential system configurations and offer a preliminary system-level analysis of a novel radial electron gun’s structural makeup (figure 3.2). In this situation, a radial electron gun can be used to treat flue gas and wastewater. Based on these concepts, two hypothetical system designs were developed, with the differences coming from the radically differing densities of the waste streams. The Flue gas application’s low flow density denotes the need for a large-area waste flow diameter for effective treatment.

The basic designs of electron accelerators used in radiation technology (direct, resonant and linear accelerators) have been successively improved over the last few decades based on new possibilities offered by the development of technology, including accelerator technology. At the same time, in the recent period, there has been a tendency to practically use the achievements of accelerator technology used to date only in research equipment in the field of nuclear physics for the construction of devices

useful for work in conditions of industrial radiation processing. Such unique solutions include a cyclic electron accelerator in short called eFFAG (electron fixed-field alternating gradient), working with a continuous wave with electron energy, beam power and dimensions adapted to the requirements of radiation technology. A distinctive feature of eFFAG accelerators is the use of a constant magnetic field (similar to cyclotrons), the use of separated magnet segments, and the use of electron dynamics similar to the synchrotron.

Another equally innovative design is an accelerator for radiation technology using a superconducting structure accelerating electrons. The acceleration section of this type is characterized by 10^6 times less surface resistance, which translates into negligible power losses and increases the efficiency of the device. At the same time, the higher goodness of the structure means less energy demand for the cooling of the structure, and the power HF it is almost entirely transmitted to the electron beam. In these conditions, it is possible to operate continuously (cw – continuous wave) with an acceleration gradient of 10 MeV/m.

Figure 3.2: RF gun design parameters (left) and components (right) [3].

Superconducting RF cavities made of Nb₃Sn, with cryogenic operation near the temperature of 4 K, exhibit minimal RF wall dissipation (about six orders of magnitude smaller than copper cavities of similar shape and size), allowing their operation at 100% RF duty cycle (continuous wave or CW operation). Fermilab has developed a novel concept for an industrial electron linac using Nb₃Sn coating technology and conduction cooling [4]. The mechanical and technological characteristics of medium energy (10 MeV) and exceptionally high average power (1000 kW) EB accelerator developed for the irradiation treatment of huge volumes from enterprises and municipalities are among the spectacular new developments was presented by Duhley et al. [2]. Besides contributing to the technical design, a full analysis of the EB accelerator’s construction and operating expenses is also provided. The estimates show that the capital cost is around \$8 per watt of beam power and that 13.5 ¢/ton/ kGy are required to carry out the irradiation.

Ecological applications, that demand high power and great electrical efficiency, and inexpensive accelerators, are related to more complex situations. The gadgets that used superconducting systems offered some optimism, but their benefits and drawbacks were not fully explored on an industrial scale. They may not achieve their predicted efficiency ratings because they require magnet cooling systems. The problem might be made better by using sources of clean energy to generate the electricity needed to power accelerators.

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4 12.1.4 – Accelerator Imaging

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Accelerators play a key role in many imaging technologies. Accelerators are able to generate X-rays via Bremsstrahlung radiation by accelerating electrons into a target, by inverse Compton scattering of photons (ICS) or by particle induced X-ray emission (PIXE) using protons and these can be used for security imaging, imaging of artwork or cultural heritage imaging. As well as imaging with X-ray we can image with neutrons allowing penetration into denser or thicker subjects.

Of these imaging technologies Bremsstrahlung is the most mature having been around for decades, however as detector technologies and computer reconstruction improves technologies need to be adapted. Different application and detector technologies currently under development require multiple angles, shorter pulses, faster energy switching or continuous operation (currently all sources are pulsed) with each requiring a new accelerator development. Nuclear resonances can be excited to identify particular substances but this requires either enormous photon fluxes or narrowband sources, neither of which can be satisfied by Bremsstrahlung. To meet this new demand ICS is required, but they must also be compact. For thinner objects like paintings, or cave art X-ray transmission imaging would provide little contrast so instead the objects are bombarded by protons to induce X-ray emission from the object itself, the spectrum of which can provide information about the paints used.

Such imaging has been used to reveal original artworks that were later painted over. For denser cargo we use the scattering of neutrons for imaging.

4.2 ACCELERATOR IMAGING

4.2.1 Importance

We live in an uncertain world and borders are continually under threat. In order to secure international borders and checkpoints its necessary to have advanced imaging technologies that can see through shipping containers and cargo to inspect what is inside. While a key target is the smuggling of guns, bombs or drugs another concern facing border security is smuggling for the purposes of tax avoidance. Cars, money, and tobacco are routinely smuggled across borders to avoid paying tax cost. Tobacco smuggling alone cost the EU 10 Billion Euros in lost revenue. As technology has evolved so has the threats that need to be detected, one example of this is Li-Ion batteries which are both a target due to their target for future smugglers and their risk of explosion, but conventional X-ray scanners are not optimised for detecting them. The use of multiple views is expected to improve the capability to scan batteries but this would be prohibitively expensive without new accelerator technologies. Using a combination of neutron and gamma-ray detectors and deep learning algorithms, substances can be identified down to their atomic level making it easier to detect certain explosives. Another concern is special nuclear materials, which look like any other dense material in X-ray scanners. Such materials need to be detected to stop smuggling of such materials into rogue states or the transport of dirty bombs. In order to detect these Nuclear Resonance Fluorescence is required that will undergo specific emission under narrowband X-ray irradiation at the correct energy such that by scanning the energy these resonances can be measured to identify the material.

4.2.2 Goal to demonstrate imaging use

The sub-task network includes industry who can directly take developments to market. As the accelerator is acting as the radiation source in an imaging system, it needs to be integrated with a detector array for use in imaging.

One of the mini projects funded by this network within IFAST is using existing non-mobile fast neutron sources to assess the effectiveness of neutrons for use in non-destructive testing and cargo scanning. This work is led by Dynaxion, which is an SME.

Another area of interest is multi-view X-ray cargo scanning, and Lancaster have been working with Rapiscan to simulate image processing for such a system and evaluating the effectiveness of the approach.

Meanwhile the Movable Accelerator for Cultural Heritage In-situ Non-destructive Analysis (MACHINA) project in Florence is working with CERN to develop a mobile RFQ to test its use with artwork. While Ion Beam Analysis like PIXE has long been used with artwork these have always been large immobile systems meaning it is only suitable for artwork that cannot be moved. For Frescos and cave paintings that cannot be moved a mobile system is required.

4.3 STRATEGY TO REACH THESE GOALS

The network is focussed on three core areas

- Advanced X-ray and neutron cargo screening
- Mobile Ion Beam Analysis systems for cultural heritage imaging
- Imaging using inverse Compton sources

We plan to have a specific meeting on each core area in 2024 to coordinate work between the different groups.

One issue with the cargo scanning area is that as its very commercial these may be issues with sharing of confidential information.

Most of the activities to date have focussed on the first two core areas as these are at a higher technology readiness level while the ICS is still in the proof of fundamental principles stage as the beam requirements for an ICS are very demanding and require a far larger scale accelerator.

The network had a call to fund mini-projects. One project was selected for funding. Fast neutron imaging is a growing field of interest for non-destructive testing (NDT) and security screening. Due to its high penetration capabilities and specificity for certain elements it is able to make images of items that no other imaging techniques (such as X-ray imaging) can.

This project has two main aims:

- Produce high quality fast neutron images of relevant objects to enhance the adoption of this imaging technique,
- Show that using multiple energies for the imaging of objects will provide additional information about the contents of the object, similarly as multi-energy imaging with X-rays.

To create the proposed images the following aspects will be addressed in this project:

- Access to a fast neutron source with variable energy
- A high resolution fast neutron imaging system

Within Europe there are several fast neutron sources that are suitable for these measurements. Typically, these facilities will provide beam time for a fee per day/week and we estimate 3 days of beamtime will be required. These costs will be covered by the IFAST project. Dynaxion has applied for beamtime at some neutron facilities and we expect to get beamtime in early 2024.

Dynaxion has developed an innovative fast neutron imaging system. It has a high detection efficiency for fast neutrons (>10%) and a spatial resolution of better than 1 mm and a field of view of 100x100mm. It is suggested to use this imaging system for these tests. Optionally a scanning platform can be provided to make larger images, for example 400x300mm. Within the IFAST collaboration a team of specialists will provide input for the images to be taken. In addition, NDT specialists will be consulted.

5 12.1.5 – Radiopharmaceutical Production

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In the continuous advancement of medicine, the incorporation of radioisotopes has revolutionized diagnostics and treatments in an extraordinary manner. These radioactive elements, emitting radiation in the form of alpha, beta, or gamma particles, have proven to be essential tools in diverse medical applications. From early disease detection to precision-guided therapy, radioisotopes have transcended conventional boundaries and emerged as crucial allies in the pursuit of health and patient well-being.

In the realm of diagnostics, the integration of radioisotopes into advanced medical imaging techniques has enabled the revelation of deep and accurate insights into the physiology and structure of the human body. Techniques such as Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET) harness the emission of gamma and positron particles, respectively, to track metabolic activity and visualize organs and tissues in detail. SPECT provides high-resolution three-dimensional images that facilitate the early detection of conditions like heart diseases and neurological disorders. PET, on the other hand, utilizes radioisotopes like fluorine-18 to map real-time metabolic activity, proving essential information for the early detection and monitoring of cancers and neurological diseases.

Within the domain of therapy, radioisotopes that release alpha and beta particles have completely changed the landscape of medical treatment choices. Alpha particles, with their high energy and short tissue range, are ideal for highly targeted therapies such as the treatment of certain types of cancer. Radioisotopes emitting beta particles, conversely, offer a broader tissue range and are used to treat a variety of conditions, including thyroid disorders and cancer. The ability to administer therapeutic doses directly to the affected tissue minimizes damage to surrounding healthy tissues.

In the era of theranostics, the fusion of diagnostics and therapy has given rise to highly personalized approaches. The same radioisotopes used for visualization and diagnosis can also be employed to deliver specific and precise therapy. This convergence revolutionizes the way we approach diseases, enabling tailored treatments that cater to the individual needs of each patient.

In summary, radioisotopes have generated a profound impact on modern medicine. From early diagnosis to targeted and personalized therapies, their versatility and precision have set a new standard in healthcare. By transcending previous limitations, radioisotopes have proven to be an invaluable resource in the pursuit of health and well-being.

5.1 STATE OF ART

The field of nuclear medicine has made significant strides, unleashing a realm of unprecedented opportunities to address clinical challenges with enhanced diagnostic precision and streamlined therapeutic interventions. The rise of innovative radiopharmaceuticals and the optimized synthesis of

pertinent radioisotopes have consistently evolved hand in hand with these breakthroughs, forging a path towards more effective medical solutions.

Noteworthy advancements in technology, such as **high-energy and high-current accelerators** [1], [2], are currently emerging for the purpose of radioisotope generation, providing a complementary edge to the existing methodologies. This progress has paved the way for a more extensive availability of several promising radionuclides, including gallium-68 [3], copper-64 [4], and zirconium-89 [5]. The evolution of **robust high-power electron accelerators** has yielded therapeutic radionuclides like scandium-47, actinium-225, and copper-67 [6]. Concurrently, alternate approaches employing both electron [7] and proton accelerators [8] are under development for the large-scale production of molybdenum-99/technetium-99m, which continues to be the most widely employed diagnostic radionuclide.

Beta emitters, including iodine-131, lutetium-177 [9], samarium-153, yttrium-90 [10], and various others, have firmly established themselves as vital therapeutic radionuclides. The clinical triumphs achieved with radiolabelled peptides and enzyme inhibitors in cancer therapy have sparked a global surge in demand for lutetium-177 over the last decade. Targeted alpha therapy stands as another pivotal realm of exploration captivating the attention of radioisotope manufacturers, researchers, and practitioners in nuclear medicine. In addition to radium-223, a multitude of other α -emitting radionuclides, such as actinium-225, astatine-211, bismuth-212, bismuth-213, lead-212, thorium-227, and terbium-149, are presently undergoing investigation for their potential in advancing radiopharmaceutical applications. The current demand for actinium-225 vastly outpaces its availability, thus prompting numerous research groups worldwide to diligently strive for the efficient production of these highly coveted α -emitting isotopes. [11] [12]

The realm of radiopharmaceuticals has undergone a constant transformation, progressing from basic ionic radioiodine to intricate coordination complexes of technetium-99m radiopharmaceuticals. At present, a spectrum of PET radioligands, along with investigational theragnostic and therapeutic agents, is undergoing scrutiny for their potential clinical utilities. This evolutionary journey has marked several notable milestones, encompassing the innovation of fresh radiochemistry techniques enabling the labelling of diverse ligands with various radionuclides, advancements in automated processes, and the availability of nonclinical assessment methodologies. These strides owe their existence to the significant contributions of scientists hailing from a myriad of disciplines.

The notion of theragnostic radioisotopes, harmonizing both diagnostic and therapeutic attributes within a single radioisotope or a compatible pair of radioisotopes, unveils a captivating blueprint for forthcoming advancements in the medical applications of radionuclides. Biomolecules adept at targeting specific cellular sites, when coupled with theragnostic radionuclides, offer a compelling avenue for clinically significant radionuclide therapy. This approach not only encompasses diagnostic precision, dosimetry calculations, and post-therapy strategizing but also embodies the essence of personalized medicine, ultimately realizing a vision where medical interventions are tailored to individual needs.

5.2 IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEM

Utilizing alpha-emitting isotopes for targeted radionuclide therapy, in combination with disease-specific targeting vectors such as antibodies or peptides, holds the promise of treating metastatic diseases by delivering radiation directly to the targeted cells. Through precise targeting, the short range and potent effects of alpha particles lead to the obliteration of nearby diseased cells while minimizing damage to healthy tissues. Recognizing this potential, the advancement of alpha-emitting radiopharmaceuticals for Targeted Alpha Therapy (TAT) constitutes a thriving domain of both academic and commercial research on a global scale. Numerous isotopes are currently undergoing clinical and preclinical assessment as potential candidates for Targeted Alpha Therapy (TAT). These include ^{149}Tb , ^{211}At , ^{212}Bi , ^{212}Pb , ^{213}Bi , ^{223}Ra , ^{224}Ra , ^{227}Th , and ^{225}Ac . Among these, ^{225}Ac stands out as a promising TAT candidate due to its 9.9-day half-life, which makes it well-suited for antibody targeting. Additionally, ^{225}Ac 's decay chain involves the emission of four alpha particles. Notably, ^{225}Ac can also serve as a generator for ^{213}Bi (with a half-life of 45.6 minutes). Clinical trials utilizing ^{213}Bi generated from a generator have demonstrated significant progress in treating different malignancies, passing clinical trials for the treatment of leukaemia, NHL, Carcinoma, neuroendocrine tumour, glioma, and melanoma., further enhancing its potential as a valuable TAT isotope.

While several clinical trials have showcased the potential of ^{225}Ac and ^{213}Bi radiopharmaceuticals for treating advanced cancers, **there is a projected shortage of ^{225}Ac supply**. This scarcity is attributed to a substantial increase in interest, despite ongoing efforts towards large-scale commercial production. At present, the most feasible approach involves utilizing the natural decay process through the $^{229}\text{Th}/^{225}\text{Ac}$ generator system. Nevertheless, only a few select global research institutions have the required capacities. These include Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) in the USA, the Institute for Transuranium Elements (ITU) in Germany, and the Leipunskii Institute for Physics and Power Engineering (IPPE) in Russia. Their collective annual production capacity is projected to be no more than 70GBq per year [13]. Additionally, the limitations imposed on Russia due to its military aggression against Ukraine have also affected the global production capabilities of ^{225}Ac and others. As a result, the European Commission is now urgently seeking new production capacity for critical isotopes, several of which are exclusively obtained from Russia or depend on precursors originating from the country. [13]

Various research endeavours have been dedicated to exploring avenues for augmenting ^{225}Ac production to meet the projected demand. Viable options encompass, (1) moderate energy proton interactions with ^{226}Ra (through nuclear transmutation), (2) subjecting ^{226}Ra to high-intensity gamma radiation (via photonuclear/Bremsstrahlung channels) and (3) high-energy proton interactions with ^{232}Th (via spallation).

5.2.1 Production of ^{225}Ac using low energy proton accelerators

This option can produce ^{225}Ac with medium-energy protons via $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction using solid or liquid target. This reaction exhibits a substantial (710 mb) cross-section peak at 16.8 MeV,

making it feasible to be executed on the numerous low-energy cyclotrons currently employed globally for medical isotope production. Another benefit of this approach is that it would avoid the co-production of ^{227}Ac . A single 20 MeV, 500 mA proton beam incident on a ^{226}Ra target (~1g) could produce a theoretical maximum of 4 TBq of ^{225}Ac per month [14]. A yield of about 2.4MBq at the EOB, 15.6 MeV, 20 mA x 5h proton beam has been obtained with this method [15].

5.2.2 Production of ^{225}Ac using electron accelerators

This alternative, $^{226}\text{Ra}(g,n)^{225}\text{Ra}$, commences by accelerating electrons, which subsequently collide with a converter. The converter absorbs the electrons energy, generating high-energy photons that then collide with the target material. This collision results in the extraction of a neutron from the atoms' nucleus, leading to the formation of ^{225}Ra . Following this, a chemical purification procedure is undertaken, effectively eliminating all actinium, including actinium-227. The refined radium solution is then subjected to decay, culminating in the production of non-carrier-added Ac-225. Experimental results measured in medical Linacs has shown a potential 48GBq of ^{225}Ac per month for a 1g ^{226}Ra source. 50 MeV, 10 mA ALTO electron Accelerator, could theoretically produce in a ^{226}Ra target (~1g) up to 56GBq per month. Given the limited yield, producing ^{225}Ac through this approach would demand the utilization of a facility equipped with notably higher electron beam currents. NorthStar Medical Radioisotopes has acquired a Rhodotron-type electron accelerators (125kW) from IBA, which will be exclusively dedicated to the production of ^{225}Ac . This production is scheduled for Q2 2024 [11].

Despite its potential, utilizing ^{226}Ra targets for (1) and (2) purposes present considerable challenges. The limited availability of the ^{226}Ra isotope and the safety hazards associated with it complicate the entire process of target manufacturing, irradiation, and recycling. The issues of radon emanation and the emission of high-energy gamma rays from its descendants further exacerbate these challenges and is a significant disadvantage of the $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$ and $^{226}\text{Ra}(g,n)^{225}\text{Ra}$ production methods.

An idea for photoproduction of ^{225}Ac and ^{227}Th utilizing a natural thorium target through a 50-70 MeV electron beam has been assessed, resulting in an anticipated annual output of 8.5 GBq for ^{225}Ac and 49 GBq for ^{227}Th , when employing a 500 kW beam.[16]

5.2.3 Production of ^{225}Ac via High Energy Proton Spallation of Thorium

This choice is the main alternative production, bombarding high-energy protons on ^{232}Th (spallation channel), $^{232}\text{Th}(p,x)^{225}\text{Ac}$ [17]. Cross-sections details is referred to: [18], [19] [20]. This approach shows potential as ^{232}Th metal does not fall under fissile material categorization as per nuclear regulations. It does not carry excessively high radioactivity, presents fewer radiological risks, and is readily accessible as a target material. The spallation of Thorium produces several other isotopes in the same target, but these impurities may be removed by chemical processing. However, the reaction requires a projectile with an extraordinarily high energy (above 70 MeV) and intensity and **only a few existing accelerators can produce proton beams with a current and energy sufficient for**

large-scale production. Production of ^{225}Ac applying high-energy protons (60-140 MeV) could generate a high yield of 96GBq per 10-d with 100mA after 10-d decay [18].

5.3 NOVEL ACCELERATOR FOR ISOTOPES PRODUCTION

The production cross-section of ^{225}Ac and ^{225}Ra , both experimentally and theoretically, exhibits a plateau as the incident proton energy approaches approximately 150 MeV by proton bombardment of Thorium. [20]. With this objective in mind, the development of an innovative **superconducting H_3^+ cyclotron**, designed to achieve **proton** energies ranging **from 70 to 150 MeV** and current of approximately 1.0 mA is a significant advancement in the field of particle acceleration. Cyclotrons within this energy spectrum are not widely established globally, yet they hold significance due to the abundance of increasingly sought-after radionuclides that fall within this range. The cyclotron will be specifically designed to accelerate H_3^+ ions. These ions will be injected from an external ion source and extracted through a stripping process. This approach holds the potential to extract proton beams of varying energies with exceptional efficiency, thereby enabling the simultaneous provision of multiple proton beams for numerous external production targets. [2] [21]

5.4 STRATEGY TO DELIVER THIS APPLICATION

5.4.1 Partners

Possible partners for collaboration could include:

TRIUMF, Canada's national laboratory: Unparalleled experience in cyclotron development is evident through decades of pioneering work in particle acceleration and nuclear physics. With a team of renowned experts, the laboratory offers a proven track record in designing, constructing, and operating cyclotrons for various applications. It is worth noting that such a machine has been proposed by them, and they have conducted an initial study. [2] [21]

PSI Laboratory in Switzerland: Invaluable experience in the realm of superconducting cyclotron development.

Centro de Investigaciones Energía Medioambiente y Tecnología, CIEMAT in Spain: The experience gained in the development of full superconducting cyclotron AMIT combined with the expertise of the superconducting magnet laboratory, constitutes an invaluable asset for similar projects.

ASG Superconductors: Boasts extensive expertise in the design of superconducting coils and cryostats. With a proven track record in developing advanced superconducting technologies, the

company has demonstrated a deep understanding of coil design intricacies and the complex thermal management systems required for efficient cryostat operation.

MEDICIS, CERN: Experience in medical research by producing novel radioisotopes.

All of them have exceptional expertise in the full design of advanced cyclotrons and particle accelerators.

5.4.2 Roadmap

Designing a superconducting cyclotron is a complex process that requires a deep understanding of particle physics, superconductivity engineering, and particle accelerator technology. The next roadmap scheme guides us through the process of conceptualizing, designing, building, and operating this advanced accelerator system.

1. **Basic design:** Define the main cyclotron parameters, energy, beam intensity, particles to accelerate, superconductor material, etc...
2. **Detailed design of components:** Magnet system, RF cavities, Vacuum, cooling and cryogenics, injection, extraction, beam dynamics, targets, control, and instrumentation.
3. **Construction and assembly:** Manufacture and assemble all components according to the final design, ensure adherence to safety and quality practices during construction.
4. **Testing and commissioning:** Conduct initial test to verify that all systems function as expected. Gradually increase energy and current intensity to achieve desired operation.
5. **Optimization and fine-tuning:** Make fine adjustments to systems to optimize cyclotron performance.
6. **Operation and maintenance:** Establish operational procedures and maintenance plans to ensure long-term functionality.
7. **Scientific research and isotope production:** Utilize the cyclotron to conduct research and isotope production.
8. **Upgrades and improvements:** As technology advances, consider upgrading and improving the cyclotron to maintain competitiveness and efficiency.

Designing and building a superconducting cyclotron requires multidisciplinary collaboration among scientists, engineers, and specialized technicians from various fields. Having financial resources, suitable facilities, and an experienced team is crucial to successfully carry out such a project.

5.4.3 Sources of founding

Funding for the development of a superconducting cyclotron can come from various sources, including government grants, research institutions, private investors, and collaborations with universities or industry partners specializing in particle accelerators and medical technology.

Keywords: Strategic Agenda for Medical Ionising Radiation Application, SAMIRA, International Atomic Energy Agency, IAEA, Nuclear Medicine Europe, NMEu, Supply Agency of the European Atomic Energy Community, ESA, Horizon Europe, European Infrastructure for Radionuclide Production, PRISMAP.

5.5 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, a high-current and high energy superconducting cyclotron has the potential to meet the expectations efficiently for alpha-emitting isotope production. This particle accelerator makes it a valuable tool in generating isotopes essential for medical treatments, research, and various other scientific applications.

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6 12.1.6 – Overcoming Obstacles to Accelerator Use

6.1 OBSTACLES PREVENTING ACCELERATOR ADOPTION BY INDUSTRY AND ENVIRONMENT CONTROL

The major barriers to EB technologies broad applications **in industry** are:

- **Economic factors** (investment cost and operational cost):
Now, there are no strict technological limits to design, construct and build accelerators achieving parameters needed for their applications on industrial scale. Many research accelerator laboratories are running machines with parameters largely exceeding industrial needs. Although the technologies are basically available, the cost-criterion moves to the first (or at least one of the top) position(s) since an industrial company must reach a profit within a reasonable time. Therefore, one can identify the first barrier: **the technologies** that are in principle feasible and proven from existing accelerators (or similar research instrumentation) on laboratory scale **must be available at reasonable cost** before they can be used in machines for industrial and societal applications. Fulfilling of this condition may still need a long-time research and development.
- **Absence of the accelerator-laboratory environment:**
This comprises two major impacts: (i) global **absence of in-house specialized and auxiliary facilities and equipment for accelerator service and maintenance** and (ii) **absence of in-house accelerator experts and staff for accelerator operation, service and maintenance**. The accelerator-selling company must provide the user with conditions that can fully compensate for the absence of the accelerator-laboratory environment. This can be achieved in several ways (or combination of them): remote customer-support; well-elaborated regular maintenance and service scheme; providing accelerator experts via different schemes (flying experts or keeping some permanent staff directly on-site); offering machines fulfilling extra specifications.
- **Problems of newcomers:**
There are newcomers on both sides: new (potential) users of accelerator technologies and new (potential) industrial companies having an ambition to produce accelerators or their components. Obviously, intensive communication between those two groups is necessary in order to match the users' needs with the producers' offer. The producers must know what the customers need and the customers shall know what is feasible and what they can ask for. The universities and research labs shall play a catalysing role in this communication. **Intensive promotion of accelerator technologies is needed.**

The major barrier to EB technologies broad applications **in the field of environment control** are:

- **Economic factors**, especially those related to the large investment costs necessary at the plant construction stage. There have been many attempts at economic analyses concerning both the investment costs and the cost of treating 1 m³ of water/wastewater. Depending on the adopted initial conditions, the costs of treatment of 1 m³ ranged from USD 0.075 to 3.17. Particularly

promising are the results indicating an increase in biodegradability after the application of small doses of 1–2 kGy of ionizing radiation. It should be expected that the practical application of radiation technologies in the treatment of water and wastewater can be really helpful for making progress in this field.

- **Lack of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators** for work in harsh environments. In the last decade, DC Electron Accelerators in the energy range (0.7-2.5 MeV) and power (100-600 kW) have been used for treatment of flue gases and industrial and municipal wastewater. Operation of such accelerators at the industrial plant level have been found necessity of further developments and development of energy efficient accelerators in higher energy range (up to 10 MeV). The increase of energy will enable treatment of thicker layers of wastewater due to larger penetration depth of electrons. The 5 MeV electrons can treat about 2 cm of liquid with 1g/cm^3 density.

6.2 SOLUTIONS IDENTIFIED

- *The absence of accelerator-laboratory environment* can be compensated by the accelerator-selling company by providing the user with **remote customer-support**. Many diagnostics, maintenance and even operational actions can be done either on-line via internet or at least using diagnostic data transferred via internet (the so-called log-files) or by running special diagnostic tools that can be distributed via internet. The development of the remote customer-support technologies is another important branch of research and technology that must be included in the strategy of industrial and societal applications of accelerators. This is obviously a dedicated branch of IT-technologies and computer science. At the same time, it is a new and attractive area of professional career for young generations of IT-experts on one side and accelerator engineers on the other one. Dedicated educational schemes and study programs are needed to bridge and bring those two expert communities together. They must be able to speak a common language, which means that the IT-experts shall understand basics of accelerator physics and technology and the accelerator experts shall understand the basics of IT. This is clearly a role for academic institutions (mainly universities) to design, offer and run such new interdisciplinary study programs. The **maintenance and service scheme** of the accelerator-selling company is basically a part of the contract between the company and the customer. Offering **machines dedicated for industrial applications** will also help to increase the application of accelerators in industry. However, different performance specifications become crucial in comparison to research accelerators. Namely: **reliability; reproducibility; high duty-factor** (long beam-on times without troubles); **operational simplicity**. An ideal accelerator would be a two-button (START & STOP) machine requiring as little operational complexity as possible. This is the goal the accelerator designers shall be aiming at and small electron accelerators used for cleaning the environment are good candidates for that. This should be the priority of developing them at the moment.
- *The problems of newcomers* can be overcome by the intensive promotion of accelerator technologies reached by (i) **education of accelerator physicists and engineers**; (ii) **attracting the specialized high-tech companies** to the market of accelerators and accelerator components; (iii) **attracting potential users** of accelerators from non-accelerator

communities (biologists, oncologists; chemists; applied physicists; environmental engineers; food-processing companies; electrical engineers; all possible suppliers of accelerator components and subsystems (IT and computer scientists; RF engineers; high-voltage engineers; control systems; magnets designers; cryogenic engineers; vacuum technologists; etc.) The universities must play a catalyzing and coordinating role in this promotion.

- The main challenge for the next **implementation of EB technologies in the field of environment control** is the **availability of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators for work in harsh environments**. To treat gases the best solution is to apply transformer accelerators with the electron energy below 1 MeV. However, to treat water and sludge linear accelerators may be the solution. Linear accelerators (linacs) using the room temperature copper RF cavities are attractive for the MeV-scale energy range required for wastewater and sludge treatment. However, these normal conducting RF cavities are constrained to operate at very low RF duty cycle due to high RF heating at the cavity walls. This low RF duty operation usually limits the average e-beam power obtainable from normal conducting linacs to few 10s of kW, making them less viable for high-volume irradiation applications. Superconducting RF cavities made of pure niobium or Nb₃Sn, with cryogenic operation near the temperature of 4 K, exhibit extremely small RF wall dissipation (about six orders of magnitude smaller than copper cavities of comparable shape and size), allowing their operation at 100% RF duty cycle (continuous wave or cw operation). SRF cavities can thus produce very high average power e-beams suitable for high-volume irradiation applications. It is also well known that SRF cavities can be more energy and cost efficient compared to copper cavities even after accounting for the energy and cost premium required for their cryogenic operation (Ciovati, 2015).

6.3 RECENT EXAMPLES OF ACCELERATOR USE

- Industry. There are now over 2000 high current, electron beam (EB) accelerators being used world-wide in industrial applications, most of which involve polymer processing. In contrast to the use of heat, which transfers only about 5–10% of input energy into energy useful for materials modification, radiation processing is very energy efficient, with 60% or more of the input energy to an accelerator being available for affecting materials. Historic markets, such as the crosslinking of wire and cable jacketing, of heat shrinkable tubings and films, of partial crosslinking of tyre components and of low-energy EB to cure or dry inks and coatings remain strong. Accelerator manufacturers have made equipment more affordable by down-sizing units while maintaining high beam currents. Very powerful accelerators with 700 kW output have made X-ray conversion a practical alternative to the historic use of radioisotopes, mainly cobalt-60, for applications as medical device sterilization. New EB end-uses are emerging, such as the development of nano-composites and nano-gels and the use of EB processing to facilitate biofuel production. These present opportunities for future research and development. Over the decades, different energy accelerators have been found to be more suitable for different industrial polymer applications:
1. Low-energy (from 120 keV to 300 keV) — printing inks; coatings for paper, wood, metals and plastics; adhesives; multilayer packaging; and surface grafting for membranes.

2. Mid-energy (from 300 keV to 5 MeV) — wire and cable insulation; heat shrinkable tubing and films; fiber modification; polymer blends with nano-particles and with natural polymers.
3. High-energy (from 5 MeV to 10 MeV) — sterilization of medical devices and some pharmaceutical and biological products; treatment of industrial and domestic effluents and sludge; treatment of lignocellulosic materials to produce ethanol biofuels.

- Environment pollution control. Examples of accelerators applications for environmental pollution control were discussed in Task 12.1.3 - Environmental Applications of Accelerators.

6.4 KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

The main challenge for the next implementation is availability of high power, low cost and high reliability accelerators for work in harsh environments. It would be extremely advisable for the IFAST Steering Committee to consider as one of the results of this project the construction of a prototype of this type of device in Europe for industrial and environmental applications, starting from 10 MeV and 20 kW machine. Some elements can be prepared using printing technology developed in the frame of IFAST.

The next challenge is for universities. Dedicated educational schemes and study programs are needed to bridge and bring together accelerator designers and engineers with accelerator users. Intensive promotion of accelerator technologies is needed covering: education of accelerator physicists and engineers, attraction of specialized high-tech companies to the market of accelerators and accelerator components; and attraction of potential users of accelerators from non-accelerator communities.

7 Conclusions

IFAST Task 12.1 has identified and studied a range of novel and important applications of accelerators. Most of these are in areas where accelerators are already widely used, in particular health, imaging and radioisotope production. The remainder are in the area of environmental applications, where there have been many studies, but rather few production facilities have been built and there is limited current commercial use, but much potential. For each identified applications, the steps still required before the application can be delivered have been described and the plans for these given. In all cases, there is much interest in doing this work and progress is often only limited by the availability of funding.

The task is also studying the general barriers to the adoption of accelerators by industry, independent of the application area. It has already identified mitigation methods for some of these and will continue to work on the remainder.

8 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ATT	intestinal parasites of the genera <i>Ascaris</i> , <i>Toxocara</i> and <i>Trichuris</i>
cfu	colony-forming unit
cw	continuous wave
d.m.	dry mass
DC	direct current
EB (eb)	electron beam
FGD	flue gas desulfurization
HFO	heavy fuel oil
PAH	polyaromatic hydrocarbons
PM	particulate matter
RF	radio frequency
SCR	selective catalytic reduction
VOC	volatile organic pollutants
WWTP	waste water treatment plant